

THE EFFECTS OF ORGANIZATIONAL PRESTIGE ON ORGANIZATIONAL IDENTIFICATION: A CASE STUDY IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

Kaya Yıldızⁱ

Assoc. Prof., Department of Primary Education,
Faculty of Education,
Abant İzzet Baysal University,
Bolu, Turkey

Abstract:

The aim of this study is to determine the relationship between organizational prestige and organizational identification perceptions of primary school teachers. In this study, in which the relationship between organizational prestige and organizational identification perception of primary school teachers was examined, the predictive correlational research model, which is one of the subcategories of correlational research models, has been used. Study group of the research constitutes of primary school teachers working in 34 primary schools located in Bolu central province as of 2017 academic year. Study group of the research constitutes of a total of 258 primary school teachers. The research data has been collected by the "Perceived Organizational Prestige Scale" and "Organizational Identification Scale. In the study, it was concluded that teachers' perceptions of organizational prestige were at "moderate" level. In the study, it was concluded that teachers' perceptions of organizational identification were at "moderate" level. In the research, it was found that there is a moderate and meaningful relationship between teachers' perceptions of the organizational prestige and organizational identification in the positive direction. Moreover, in the study, it was found out that organizational prestige is a significant predictor of organizational identification behaviors.

Keywords: organizational prestige, organizational identification, primary school teachers

1. Introduction

Changes in the world make it necessary to change in the field of education as well as in economic, social, political and cultural fields. In recent years, all countries have made many innovations and changes in order to improve their education systems. In recent

ⁱ Correspondence: email yildiz_k1@ibu.edu.tr

years, all countries have made many innovations and changes in order to improve their education systems. One of the areas where the fastest changes are experienced in Turkey is education. The enhancement and dissemination of knowledge resulting from technological developments necessitated constant questioning and restructuring of the current situation in the education sector. Although many legal arrangements have been made to increase the efficiency and success of education organizations, it is seen that the human element of education should be developed and activated more than the legal regulations when it is taken into account that the functioning, raw materials and product of education organizations are human (Leblebici, 2016).

Today, the organizations that want to achieve their organizational goals have to deal with the human factor, which is the most important and fundamental factor of organizations, with sensitivity. When it comes to educational institutions, it should be known that teachers, who are employees of these institutions, are the most important factors and their sense of belonging, in other words, the need to be affiliated to a strong identity must be met as a basic need. Organizations expect from their employees to go beyond the emotions such as loving their workplaces, having a sense of loyalty and not having an intention to leave the workplace, and the individuals are asked to adopt the organization to the extent that they identify their individual identities with the organization (İşçan, 2006). When teachers are identified with their schools, they perceive the success of the institution as their achievements, and the failure of the institution as their own failure. The perception of prestige related to the school is very important in identification with the school. It is expected that the high prestige of the organization and high perception of organizational diversity by employees is effective in identifying employees themselves with their organizations. The greater the perceived reputation of the group, the stronger gets the individuals' tendency to identify themselves with it, and vice versa (March and Simon, 1975; Özgür, 2015). In this case, organizational prestige perception is an important determinant of organizational identification. In this study, the concepts of organizational prestige and organizational identification, which are important in the achievements and objectives of the school, are emphasized.

1.2 Organizational Prestige

In our everyday life, the society moves away from some institutions and organizations or approaches to them with more interest by assigning an epithet to them and one of these epithets is prestige. The concept of prestige, which is used in psychology and sociology at the outset, then introduced into the management and organization fields, means the social and economic situation which gives superiority to an individual or a social group in their relationship with an individual or a social group (TDK, 2018). The word prestige is etymologically a French word used as "prestige" in the original language. Its meaning in French is being respected, being valuable and reliable and respectability (Özgür, 2015). Despite the fact that March and Simon was the first one who found out the concept of organizational prestige with his researches in 1958, Meal and Ashforth (1992) was the first one who conducted a comprehensive research on

organizational prestige. As a result of the research conducted on the issue, Meal and Ashforth (1992), defines the term as a perception that is emerged as a result of the comparison of the affiliated organization and the other organizations made by the employees of an organization (Bardakoğlu and Akgündüz, 2016). March and Simon (1958) considered organizational prestige perception as "*evaluations of employees on their own institutions, individually and as a society*". Dutton, Dukerich and Harquail (1994) describes organizational prestige perception as "*evaluation of employees on their institutions by taking into account the views of every individuals outside the institution*". Smidts, Pruyn and Van Riel (2001) consider the perception of organizational prestige as "*the evaluation of institutions on their own prestige according to the information obtained from various sources*". Carmeli and Freund (2002) describe the perception of organizational prestige as "*the evaluations of institutions and employees on the parties who directly and indirectly show deference to them*".

Organizational prestige is the sum of the impressions of parties outside the organization, which are connected with the organization, as the result of their association with the organization. Organizational prestige refers not only to the set of the values an institution has and perspectives of its representatives, but also to the everyone's interest, connection and perception of the topic who has a direct or indirect relationship with the organization (Bakan, Erşahan and Kaya, 2016). Today, organizations' prestige-based structure makes it necessary for organizations to position themselves positively in this area. Organizational prestige is now highly determinative and guiding for employees. While the interest and emphasis given by the employees in organizational prestige is increasing, it is also in question that this element is regarded as an element of competition among the organizations. In this way, organizational prestige is an element which can affect the recognition, prefer ability and competition of organizations at the same time (Şirin, 2018). It is expected that the level of identification of the employees with their organization will be affected positively from the organizations with a strong identity, which is perceived as prestigious and known in this respect. It is possible to consider that the organizational prestige perceived in this framework can play a role in the self-classification of the individual and in the process of identification with the organization (Tak and Çiftçiöğlü, 2009).

1.3 Organizational Identification

Identification is a concept which has psychological and sociological aspects in terms of describing an individual's social cohesion with a group or other individuals and identifying herself/himself as a member of a group. Identification, which is one of the important issues of social psychology that investigates the influence of social conditions on human, was first used by Laswell (1935) as a psychological and sociological concept. The identification of employees with their organizations in the literature is mainly explained in the context of Social Identity Theory (Tajfel, 1987; Özgür, 2015). According to the Social Identity Theory, individuals tend to classify themselves and others within different social groups. In this way, they organize their social environment and place themselves and others in this framework. Moreover, according to the relevant theory,

individuals perceive themselves as a real or symbolic member of a group based on their classification and they are socially identified by developing a sense of belonging (Tak and Çiftçioğlu, 2009). The organizational identification, adapted to the field of organization by Ashforth and Mael (1989), has been a concept that keeps up-to-date at all times and attracts the attention of researchers. With the most explicit expression, the organizational identification, which is defined as the link between the individual and the organization, tries to explain and understand the attitudes and behaviors of the individual in the organization and the underlying reasons for their attitudes and behaviors (Leblebici, 2016).

The most widely accepted definitions of organizational identification are the definitions made by Ashforth and Mael (1989) and Dutton et al. (1994). While Ashforth and Mael (1989) defines organizational identification as an organizational belonging and the perception of being with it, Dutton et al. (1994) defines organizational identification as the level of identification with the same attitudes that the individual believes in defining the organization. In these definitions, the relation between organizational identification and the employee and the organization has been underlined, and the perception of the employee towards the organization and the definition of the organization made by the employee according to herself/himself has been mentioned (Özgür, 2015).

The place and significance of organizational identification in the field of organizational behavior increased in 1989 when the Social Identity Theory was adapted by Ashforth and Mael to organizations. The studies conducted afterwards have gained a theoretical background. Understanding what mechanisms are guiding employees' attitudes and behaviors towards work may only be possible by identifying employees' perceptions of the organizations they work with. The fact that underlies this perception is the level of the identification of an employee with her/his organization (Polat, 2009). In this context, organizational identification is the perception of the individuals as belonging to a certain organization and to define themselves according to the organization of which they are a member. With this object in mind, organizational identification will have positive consequences for both the individual and the organization. From the point of view of the individuals, their need to belong to an organization will be met and their self-esteem and core values will be developed. It will have a positive impact on higher motivation and job performance in terms of the organization and will reduce the intentions of individuals to leave the job, and the organizations will reach out to their longer-term goals and organizational achievements through individuals identified with their organizations. The most fundamental effect of organizational identification is that the individuals will act in the interests of the organizations, which they are identified with.

Organizations want to work with individuals identified with their organizations to achieve their long-term goals. The question of what needs to be done to identify the individual with the organization is an important question. The point that should be considered by the organizations in searching for an answer to this question is that identification of individuals with the organization is beyond the economic actions

(Dutton et al. 1994). In order for individuals to increase their perceptions of organizational identification, the sense of belonging of individuals to their organizations and compliance of the individual and organizational goals must be ensured. The stronger the identification of an individual with a group, the more likely it is that their goal is in compliance with their perception of group norms (March and Simon, 1975). Organizational identification makes the working life of the individual more meaningful, strengthens their organizational affiliation, supports control activities, and optimizes the individual's potential. The individuals identified with the organization make more efforts on behalf of the organization because they perceive themselves as a part of the organization (Ashforth and Mael, 2001). Organizations want to strengthen their employees' identification sense as they believe that identification affects performance of the employees (Tüzün and Çağlar, 2008). The more the individuals are convinced that their needs will be met by joining a group, the more their cohesion with the group increases (Bursalıoğlu, 2002).

Organizational identification is a useful structure for understanding the exchange relationship between the individual and the organization. As people become more identified with their organizations, their level of thinking and acting in line with the organizational perspective increases (Tüzün and Çağlar, 2008). The reason for this is that individuals who identify themselves with the organization believe that behaviors beneficial to the organization will be beneficial to themselves. Such an employee strongly believes in organizational values and goals and accepts them or performs her/his job willingly (Meydan and Polat, 2013). An employee identified with the organization with a real sense can see herself/himself as a member who sustains the organization (Celep, 2014). When individuals are identified with their organizations, they impersonate themselves with the organization (Mael and Ashforth, 1995).

1.4 The Relation between Organizational Identification and Organizational Prestige

When the organizational identification is defined as the individuals' perception of belonging to a particular organization and defining themselves according to the organization (Meal and Ashforth, 1992), it can be said that perceived organizational prestige can be effective in self-classification of the individual and in developing the sense of belonging between the organization and the individual, and in this way, it is possible to say that the individual can identify herself/himself with the organization. When the conducted studies are examined, it has been found out that organizational perception at a high level has a positive and significant effect on employees' organizational identification levels (Polat, 2009). It is possible to say that if the prestige of the organization is high and the group has a positive belief in it, members of the organization will become more identifiable with their organizations. According to March and Simon (1975), an individual's tendency to identify with a high standing organization is more likely than the tendency to identify with a low-profile organization.

Many studies have been conducted on variables of organizational identification and perceived organizational prestige. In these studies, these two variables are

addressed from different perspectives. In these studies, perceived organizational prestige was regarded as a predecessor of organizational identification. In his study, Polat (2009) accepted the perceived organizational prestige as predecessor of organizational identification. According to March and Simon (1975), identification is important from three perspectives, one of them is the high recognition level of the group. In these studies, March and Simon (1975) accepted the perceived organizational prestige as predecessor of organizational identification. It is stated that the perceived reputation of the group affects the degree of strength of identification with the group. The greater the perceived reputation of the group, the stronger gets the individuals' tendency to identify themselves with it, and vice versa. The less perceived reputation of the group is, the weaker get the individuals' tendency to identify themselves with the group (March and Simon, 1975).

In his studies, Meal and Ashforth (1992) examined the influence of individual and organizational predecessors on organizational identification. Meal and Ashforth (1992) has come to the conclusion from these predecessors that there is a positive and statistically significant effect of organizational prestige and organizational distinctiveness on organizational identification. Lipponen, Helkama, Olkkonen and Juslin (2005) conducted studies on the organizational prestige he considered to be an important predictor of organizational identification and found a statistically significant relationship between the two variables. Iyer, Bomber and Barefield (1997) identified organizational and individual predecessors and successors that influence organizational identification in his studies. As a result of the research, organizational prestige perceived from organizational factors has been found to be a positive and statistically significant effect on organizational identification.

Today, as in any other area, the field of education has brought with it new understandings and approaches. The focal point of this change that has been being experienced today is the increasing needs of people and changing environmental conditions. Schools that reflect all aspects of open systems are the organizations most affected by these changes and developments. Today's educational organizations have to respond to the needs of both internal and external stakeholders if they want to constitute a respectable, attractive and successful identity. The perceptions of teachers of schools that have created a respectable, successful and attractive identity will also be affected by this situation. Teachers will perceive their institutions as respectable and that will increase their willingness to work and work-oriented performance at school. It is considered to be important to determine the level of perception of teachers' organizational prestige and organizational identification and assert the fact that whether these behaviors are related to each other or not, in particular, in primary schools which is regarded as the key point of the system.

1.5 Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to determine the relationship between organizational prestige and organizational identification perceptions of primary school teachers.

2. Material and Methods

In this study, in which the relationship between organizational prestige and organizational identification perception of primary school teachers was examined, the predictive correlational research model, which is one of the subcategories of correlational research models, has been used. In predictive correlational researches, it is aimed to determine the existence of covariance between the variables by examining the relations between the variables (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç-Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz and Demirel, 2013).

2.1 Study Group

Study group of the research constitutes of primary school teachers working in 34 primary schools located in Bolu central province as of 2017 academic year. Study group of the research constitutes of a total of 258 primary school teachers. Demographic information on teachers included in the study group is given in Table 1.

Analyzing Table 1, according to demographic information of teachers working in primary schools, 62.8% of teachers are female and 37.2% of them are male in the study group. In age distribution of teachers, the highest level of accumulation is in "41-45 age" group with 27.1%. The least accumulation is in "51 years old and older" group with a rate of 9.7%. According to teachers' professional seniority, the highest accumulation is in "21-25 years" of experience with 27.9%. The least accumulation is in group of teachers with "26 years and more" seniority with a rate of 9.7%.

Table 1: Demographic information of the teachers who participate to the study

		<i>f</i>	%
Gender	Female	181	62,8
	Male	77	37,2
Age	25-30 age range	22	8,6
	31-35 age range	45	17,4
	36-40 age range	41	15,9
	41-45 age range	70	27,1
	46-50 age range	55	21,3
	51 + age range	25	9,7
Teaching Experience	1-5 years	15	5,8
	6-10 years	30	11,6
	11-15 years	51	19,8
	16-20 years	65	25,2
	21-25 years	72	27,9
	26 + years	25	9,7
Total: 258			100,0

2.2 Collection of Data

The research data has been collected by the "Perceived Organizational Prestige Scale", which is developed by Mael and Ashforth (1992), adapted to Turkish by Tak and Çiftçioğlu (2009) and adapted to educational institutions by Özgür (2015), and

"Organizational Identification Scale", which is developed by Mael and Ashforth (1992) adapted to Turkish by Tak and Aydemir (2004). Firstly, the most suitable assessment instrument for the research has been determined by making a literature review. After that, permission was obtained from the researchers for the use of the determined scale. The scales have been applied to primary school teachers. General information about the scales has been given to the teachers and the purpose of the study has been explained. Volunteering is the basis for participation in the research. In 2017-2018 academic year, 385 teachers are working in 34 primary schools located in Bolu central district borders. Scales have been handed out by the researcher to the teachers who are working in the primary school during the application phase and who voluntarily wanted to participate in the research. A total of 258 scales have been collected from the given scales by excluding the scales which include empty, missing markings, multiple markings, etc., and they have been taken into statistical analysis processes. 85.2% of teachers have been reached.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

A. Perceived Organizational Prestige Scale

The Perceived Organizational Prestige Scale is a scale that is developed by Mael and Ashforth (1992), adapted to Turkish by Tak and Çiftçioğlu (2009) and adapted to educational institutions by Özgür (2015). The reliability of the scale consisting of 8 items and one dimension was calculated by Mael and Ashforth (1992) as 0.77. Tak and Çiftçioğlu (2009) calculated the reliability of this scale as .84 in his studies. In the study conducted by Özgür (2015), the reliability coefficient of the Perceived Organizational Prestige scale was determined as 0.85. Tak and Çiftçioğlu (2009) analyzed the validity of the structure of the scale with descriptive factor analysis and as a result of the analysis, it was observed that the eigenvalue of the scale consists of a single sub-dimension larger than 1. The factor loadings of the items in the scale range from 0.63 to 0.86. The total variance explained by the scale is 49%. Tak and Çiftçioğlu (2009) also performed confirmatory factor analysis of the scale and found that the one-factor structure shown good agreement ($\chi^2(20) = 134$, $\chi^2/df = 6.7$, GFI= 0.90, AGFI= 0.82, CFI=0.89, RMSR=0.086, RMSEA=0.14). The implementation of the Perceived Organizational Prestige Scale, which had not been applied to teachers in educational institutions before, was carried out in educational institutions by Özgür (2015). In the study conducted by Özgür (2015) some scale-related regulations were made, and items 7 and 8 were found to be difficult to understand, thus, these items were re-expressed by researcher and supervisor and studies were reanalyzed. Özgür (2015) reexamined the structural validity of the Organizational Prestige scale. Firstly, skewness (-.25) and kurtosis (-.36) values were calculated to determine the suitability of the data for factor analysis and it was determined that it is suitable for the analysis. The one-factor structure of the scale was then tested by confirmatory factor analysis. The results of the analysis show that the goodness of fit values ($\chi^2/df: 3.07$, GFI: .98, AGFI: .94, CFI: .98, SRMR: .034, RMSEA: .064) confirm the one-factor structure of the scale in this study sample. In the study conducted by Özgür (2015), the reliability coefficient of the Perceived Organizational

Prestige scale was determined as .85. In the Perceived Organizational Prestige scale, items 4 6 7 and 8 are reverse coding items. The Perceived Organizational Prestige scale is designed as 5-point (Likert) type and the rating options are provided as follows: (1) strongly disagree, (2) disagree, (3) neutral, (4) agree, (5) strongly agree. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the Perceived Organizational Prestige Scale in this study was found to be .82. These findings indicate that the measurement tool is reliable (Alpar, 2014).

B. The Organizational Identification Scale

The Organizational Identification Scale is a scale developed by Mael and Ashforth (1992) and adapted to Turkish by Tak and Aydemir (2004). The Organizational Identification Scale consists of 6 items and one dimension. In order to test the structural validity of the organizational identification scale, Tak and Aydemir (2004) conducted an exploratory factor analysis. As a result of the exploratory factor analysis, it was found out that there is a single sub-dimension, of which eigenvalue is greater than 1, and factor loads of the items in the scale vary between the range of 0.79 and 0.87. The total variance explained by the scale is 37%. In the adaptation study conducted by Tak and Aydemir (2004), confirmatory factor analysis results ($\chi^2(9) = 25$, $\chi^2/df = 2.77$, GFI=0.97, AGFI=0.94, CFI=0.96, RMSR=0.037, RMSEA=0.077) also indicated that the strength of the scale to measure the organizational identification variable is high. Mael and Ashforth (1992) determined the reliability level of the scale as .87. Tak and Aydemir (2004) used this scale in his studies and determined the level of reliability as .88. Tüzün (2006) used the organizational identification scale in his study and found the level of reliability as 0.77. In the study conducted by Özgür (2015), reliability level of the organizational identification scale was found as .75. In this study, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the Organizational Identity Scale was determined as .90. These findings indicate that the measurement tool is reliable (Alpar, 2014).

2.4 Data Analysis

The normality distributions of the scales and sub-dimensions were examined first in order to determine the statistical methods to be used in the analysis of data obtained from the Organizational Prestige and Organizational Identification scales. The skewness and kurtosis coefficients of the scales and sub-dimensions vary between the range of -.487 and .225 depending on the variables to be examined. The determination of the skewness and kurtosis coefficients between ± 1 values indicates that the scales and sub-dimensions do not deviate extremely from the normal distribution (Büyüköztürk, Çokluk and Köklü, 2011). Statistical methods based on the assumption of normal distribution are used for the analysis of data in accordance with the obtained results. The frequency and percentage distributions of the demographics of the teachers in the study group, then the arithmetic mean and standard deviation scores of the scales were calculated. A simple linear regression analysis technique was used to determine the relationship between teachers' perceptions of organizational prestige and organizational identification. The statistical analyzes of the data were performed in the SPSS program, the significance was tested at a minimum level of $p < .05$ and presented in tabular form in line with the purposes of the findings. While interpreting the results

obtained towards solving sub-questions in the research; "1.00-1.80 None", "1.81-2.61 Low", "2.62-3.42 Moderate", "3.4-4.23 High" and "4.24-5.00 Very High" values were used.

3. Findings

Findings related to the teachers' perceptions of organizational prestige and organizational identification were given under the headings.

3.1 Teachers' Perception of Organizational Prestige and Organizational Identification

The findings related to the teachers' perception of organizational prestige and organizational identification are given in Table 2.

Table 2: The arithmetic mean and standard deviation scores of the teachers' perception of organizational prestige and organizational identification

	f	$\bar{X}$	sd
Organizational Prestige	258	3.38	.61
Organizational Identification	258	3.24	.57

The arithmetic mean and standard deviation scores of the teachers' perception of organizational prestige and organizational identification are given in Table 2. In general, teachers' perceptions of organizational prestige ($\bar{X}$ =3.38, sd=.61) are at "moderate" level. Teachers' perceptions of organizational identification ($\bar{X}$ =3.24, sd=.57) are at "moderate" level.

3.2 The Relationship between Teachers' Perception of Organizational Prestige and Organizational Identification

Findings Related to the Relationship between Teachers' Perception of Organizational Prestige and Organizational Identification:

Table 3: ANOVA Analysis Results on the Prediction of Organizational Identification

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
1 Regression	12.754	1	12.754	48.937	.000 ^b
Residual	66.717	256	.261		
Toplam	79.471	257			

When Table 3 is examined, it is determined that the model of the predictions of Organizational Identification levels and proactive behaviors is significant according to the ANOVA results ($F_{(1,256)} = 48.937, p < .05$).

Table 4: Standard Regression Analysis Results on the Prediction of Organizational Identification

	B	Std. Error B	β	T	Sig.
Constant	2.250	.254		8.846	.000
Organizational Prestige	.418	.060	.401	6.995	.000
R= 0.401 R ² =0.160 F _(1,256) = 48.937, p<.05) p=0.000					

When Table 4 is examined, it is seen that there is a positive and moderate relationship between Teachers' Perceptions of Organizational Prestige and Organizational Identification (r=0.401).

It provides a moderate and significant relationship with Organizational Prestige and Organizational Identification scores (R= 0.401, R²= 0.160, p<.001). Organizational Prestige and Organizational Identification explain the 16,0% of the total variance (variable) of behaviors as significant. Organizational Prestige and Organizational Identification are a significant predictor of behaviors.

Identification of teachers with institutions may have an impact on the proactive behavior of teachers. It is therefore important to investigate the effect of identification on teachers' proactive behavior.

4. Results and Discussion

In this study, the relationship between organizational prestige and organizational identification perceptions of primary school teachers was investigated. In the study, it was concluded that teachers' perceptions of organizational prestige were at "moderate" level. There is a limited number of studies in the literature conducted on the teachers' perceptions of organizational prestige. In studies conducted by Özgür (2015), Leblebici (2016), Uğurlu and Ceylan (2013) on the literature, it is concluded that the teachers' perceptions of organizational prestige are at "moderate" level. These findings are consistent with the results of the research. In the research conducted by Demiröz (2014) and Gürbüz (2008), it is concluded that teachers' perceptions of organizational prestige are at a positive level.

In the most general sense, perceived organizational prestige is the thoughts, feelings and perceptions of individuals who work for an organization on the way they perceive other people's organization. The high level of organizational prestige is beneficial for organizations to be respected by their internal and external stakeholders, to be valued and esteemed, to be seen in a different position and to protect their interests (Tutar, 2008). The education system has to identify new objectives that can sustain the reason for existence and search for ways to become functional in the new century (Özden, 1998). In order for educational institutions to fulfill the expected function, it is necessary to increase the quality of education (Özdemir, 2003). Schools are the smallest sub-units formed to meet educational expectations. When the objectives of the schools are evaluated, the importance of the high level of success in examinations

conducted in schools across the country has been brought to the forefront. Academically successful schools have achieved the most important institutional objectives. Schools with high achievement levels will also increase their recognition in their surroundings and parents, students and teachers will perceive these schools as different from other schools. This difference will positively affect the school's reputation and the level of demand for these schools will also increase. Teachers will perceive these schools as prestigious and will want to work in these schools (Özgür, 2015).

In the study, it was concluded that teachers' perceptions of organizational identification were at "moderate" level. Studies on teachers' perceptions of organizational identification are included in the literature. In studies conducted by Özgür (2015), Yıldız (2013), Lelebici (2016), Taşkın (2016), Akpınar (2014), Tüzün and Çağlar (2009) in the literature, it is concluded that teachers' perceptions of organizational identification are at "moderate" level. These findings are consistent with the results of the research. In the research conducted by Nartgün and Kalay (2014), Yetim (2010), Özdemir (2010), Çakınberk, Derin and Demirel (2011), Ekinçi (2015) and Yörük and Sağban (2012), it is concluded that teachers' perception of organizational identification is at high level. In the study conducted by Balcı, Fidan, Cereci and Acar (2012), it is concluded that the school principals' perception of organizational identification is at high level.

Organizational identification has become one of the modern management approaches with the adaptation of the Social Identity Theory, developed by Tajfel and Turner, into the organizational domain by Mael and Ashforth (1992), which became the domain of social psychology. Organizational identification is the process of integration and harmonization of the goals of the individual with the objectives of the organization (Mael and Ashforth, 1992) or emotional connection between the organization and the individual (Reade, 2001). Knowing similarities and differences between individuals and organizations also enables organizations to achieve their goals and affects the attitudes and behaviors of individuals towards organizational goals. Identification of the individual with the organization becomes a critical factor in reaching long-term goals. Organizational identification is a concept that notices the importance of the relationship between an employee and an organization. Perception of the relationship between employees and the organization is important for many reasons. As knowing the similarities and differences between employees and organizations will also mean knowing the nature of the relationship between these two structures, it seems to be a method for predicting the attitudes and behaviors of the individual towards institutional goals. It has become important for teachers to be satisfied with the institution they are working for, to have strong sense of belonging to the institution and to identify themselves with their institutions. Identification of teachers with institutions will be a significant method to achieve the long-term goals at a lower cost. Teachers, identified with the organization, tend to see themselves as representatives of the organization when interacting with people outside the organization, so they exhibit different attitudes to those who take a firm stand against the organizational values and goals by prioritizing institution's interests in taking decisions related to the strategic

and business-oriented opportunities (Yıldız, 2013). When teachers identify themselves with the organization, the work they do becomes more meaningful to them and thus they are more motivated towards their work. Employees identified with their organizations will voluntarily adopt the behaviors that support their organizations and will voluntarily make efforts for the benefit of the organization (İşcan, 2006).

In the research, it was found that there is a moderate and meaningful relationship between teachers' perceptions of the organizational prestige and organizational identification in the positive direction. Moreover, in the study, it was found out that organizational prestige is a significant predictor of organizational identification behaviors. Studies that examine teachers' perceptions of organizational identification are included in the literature. Studies conducted by Özgür (2015) and Leblebici (2016) also show that there is a moderately positive relationship between teachers' perceptions of organizational prestige and organizational identification. According to Ashforth and Mael (1989), the more the organization is perceived by its members as prestigious organization than other organizations, the greater the identification will increase. In a study supporting this knowledge, Smidts et al. (2001) concluded that perceived external prestige has a positive effect on organizational identification. In his study, Riketta (2005) examined relationship of organizational identification with many variables and found a positive and moderate relationship between organizational prestige and organizational identification. In another study, Bhattacharya, Rao, and Glynn (1995) determined that the high level of organizational prestige perceived from the factors that affect the level of identification of a customer with a company also affects the level of identification of customers with this organization in the positive direction Carmelli, Gilat and Weisberg (2006), an important researcher in the field of organizational prestige, has investigated the relationship between organizational prestige perceptions of stakeholders (customers, competitors and suppliers) and organizational identification perceptions of employees at a workplace. According to the results of the research, it was found that there is a positive relationship between stakeholder group perceptions of prestige related to organization and organizational identification levels of employees. According to Pratt, who identifies an individual with a social need, the sense of belonging lies at the heart of the identification (Pratt, 1998). Pratt (1998) stated that having a positive prestige is effective on organizational identification. As a result of the conducted studies, Mael and Ashforth (1992) found a positive and meaningful relationship between organizational identification and perceived organizational prestige. It was carried out by Dutton et al. (1994). In the study, Dutton et al. (1994) stated that individuals who highly identify themselves with their organizations are individuals who believe that they are providing valuable outputs for their organizations, and he explained the relationship between the prestige perception related to the organization and identification of individuals with organizations through a model.

When the impact of perceived organizational prestige on organizational identification is generally evaluated, it is known that identification is a situation related to the groups which are perceived as prestigious and distinguishable. In this case, it can

be said that employees who perceive the organization as prestigious are more likely to be identified with their organizations. Perceived organizational prestige is a situation that has significant influence on organizational identification. The fact that schools work with teachers that are identified with them is an important factor in the success of schools. Teachers will contribute positively to the success of the schools, which they perceive as prestigious, while teachers' need for sense of belonging are addressed. The reputation of the institution will increase after the success attained by the school, its level of recognition will increase and the need of teachers for belonging to a strong identity will be met.

As a result, teachers should be provided the feeling that they belong to the school, their knowledge, skills and abilities should be supported and their development in line with the objectives of the school should be supported. In order to achieve this, school administrators have a lot of work to do. Teachers should be provided to perceive that they are both materially and spiritually valued by the school. It is necessary to start this process immediately after the teachers have started their duties in the school. In order to increase organizational identification, democratic, participatory and open working environments should be established. The school principal should improve the working conditions of the teachers, appreciate their achievements, and ensure that the teachers are proud of being a teacher of this school. Improving knowledge, skills and abilities through the school environment will affect teachers' acceptance of school identity and it will contribute to the identification of teachers with schools. In order to improve the school's prestige perception, physical arrangements can be made by improving school facilities and equipment in public schools. This will also affect the increase in success and the identification of teachers with their institutions. Family participation activities, seminars, promotion program for schools and teachers often held in private schools for increasing the prestige perception can also be organized in public schools. Prestige perceptions perceived by teachers, administrators, students and the external environment related to schools should be evaluated at different times and the negative perceptions must be corrected. In order to increase teachers' image perceptions, administrators can directly perform activities related to them, and they can influence their thoughts by conducting activities related to the external environment. In order to strengthen the image of the school, concrete items such as logo, emblem, uniform should be used effectively. This positively affects the identification of teachers and students with their schools, and the school's recognition level in the environment will increase.

References

1. Akpınar, A., 2014. Okullardaki insan ilişkileri düzeyi ile öğretmenlerin örgütsel özdeşleşme düzeyleri arasındaki ilişki. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Uşak Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Uşak.

2. Alpar, R., 2014. Spor sađlık ve eđitim bilimlerinden örneklerle uygulamalı istatistik ve geçerlik - güvenilirlik (3. Baskı). Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.
3. Ashforth, B.E. and Mael, F., 1989. Social identify theory and the organization. *Academy of Management Review*, 14 (1), 20-39.
4. Ashforth, B. E. and Mael, F. A., 2001. Identification in work, war, sports, and religion: Contrasting the benefits and risks. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 31(2), 197-222.
5. Bakan, İ., Erşahan, B. and Kaya, İ., 2016. Örgütsel kimliđin ve örgütsel prestijin, örgütsel vatandaşlık üzerindeki etkisi: bir alan araştırması, *Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 6 (1), 69-88.
6. Balcı, A., Baltacı, A., Fidan, T., Cereci, C. and Acar, U., 2012. Örgütsel sosyalleşmenin, Örgütsel özdeşleşme ve örgütsel vatandaşlıkla ilişkisi: ilköđretim okulu yöneticileri Üzerinde bir araştırma. *Eđitim Bilimleri Araştırmaları Dergisi* 2 (2), 47-74.
7. Bardakođlu, Ö. and Akgündüz, Y., 2016. Otel çalışanlarının örgütsel prestij ve psikolojik güçlendirme algılarının işbirliđi davranışlarına etkisi. *Uluslararası Yönetim İktisat ve İşletme Dergisi (Int. Journal of Management Economics and Business)*, 12 (30), 145-158.
8. Bhattacharya, C. B., Rao, H., and Glynn, M. A., 1995. Understanding the bond of identification: an investigation of its correlates among art museum members. *The Journal of Marketing*, 59, 46-57.
9. Bursalıođlu, Z., 2002. Okul yönetiminde yeni yapı ve davranış. 12. Basım. Ankara: Pegem A Yayıncılık.
10. Büyüköztürk, Ş., Çokluk, Ö. and Köklü, N., 2011. Sosyal bilimler için istatistik (7.baskı). Ankara: Pegem.
11. Büyüköztürk, Ş., Çakmak, E., Akgün, Ö., Karadeniz, Ş., and Demirel, F., 2009. *Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri*, Ankara: Pegem Akademi,
12. Çakınberk, A. Derin, N. and Demirel, E., 2011. Örgütsel özdeşleşmenin örgütsel bađlılıkla biçimlenmesi: Malatya ve Tunceli özel eđitim kurumları örneđi. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 3(1), 89-121.
13. Carmeli, A., and Freund, A., 2002. The relationship between work and workplace attitudes and perceived external prestige. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 5(1), 51-68.
14. Carmeli, A., Gilat, G., and Weisberg, J., 2006. Perceived external prestige, organizational identification and affective commitment: a stakeholder approach. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 9(2), 92-104.
15. Celep, C., 2014. Eđitim örgütlerinde örgütsel adanma. Ankara: Nobel Yayıncılık.
16. Demiröz, S., 2014. Öđretmenlerin örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışları, örgütsel imaj algıları ve öđrenci başarıları arasındaki ilişki. Yayımlanmamış Doktora tezi. Hacettepe Üniversitesi/ Eđitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
17. Dutton, J. E., Dukerich, J.M. , Hardquail, C.V., 1994. Organizational images and member identification. *Administration Sciences Quarterly*, 39, 239-263.

18. Ekinci, S., 2015. İlk ve ortaokul öğretmenlerinin örgütsel özdeşleşme ve örgütsel sinizm düzeylerine ilişkin görüşleri: Bolu ili örneği. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans tezi, Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Bolu.
19. Gürbüz, S., 2008. Yönetici, Öğretmen ve Velilere Göre Ankara İli Özel ve Kamu İlköğretim Okullarının Kurumsal İmajı. Yayınlanmamış Doktora Tezi. Ankara: Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
20. İşcan, Ö.F., 2006. Dönüştürücü/etkileşimci liderlik algısı ve örgütsel özdeşleşme ilişkisinde bireysel farklılıkların rolü. Akdeniz İ.İ.B.F. Dergisi 11,160-177.
21. Iyer, M.V., Bamber E.M. and Barefield, R.M., 1997. Identification of accounting firm alumni with their former firm: antecedents and outcomes. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 22(3/4), 315-336.
22. Leblebici, E., 2016. Öğretmen algılarına göre meslek liselerinde örgütsel imaj, örgüt kültürü ve örgütsel özdeşleşme arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Mevlana Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Konya.
23. Lipponen, J., Helkama, K., Olkkonen, M. E., ve Juslin, M., 2005. Predicting the different profiles of organizational identification: a case of shipyard subcontractors. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 78(1), 97-112.
24. Mael, F., and Ashforth, B. E., 1995. Loyal from day one: biodata, organizational identification, and turnover among newcomers. *Personnel Psychology*, 48, 309-333.
25. Mael, F., and Ashforth, B. E., 1992. Alumni and their alma mater: a partial test of the reformulated model of organizational identification. *Journal Of Organizational Behavior*, 13(2), 103-123.
26. March G.J. and Simon, H.A., 1975. Örgütler. (çev. Ömer BOZKURT ve Oğuz ONARAN), Ankara: TODAİE Yayınları.
27. Meydan, C. H., and Polat, M., 2013. Bir örgüt formu olarak okul ile özdeşleşmede akademik başarı ve özdisiplinin rolü. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 38(167), 27-40.
28. Nartgün, Ş.S. and Kalay, M. (2014). Öğretmenlerin örgütsel destek, örgütsel özdeşleşme ile örgütsel sinizm düzeylerine ilişkin görüşleri. *Turkish Studies – International Periodical For The Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*, 9(2), 1361-1376.
29. Özdemir, A., 2010. Örgütsel özdeşleşmenin algılanan örgütsel destek, cinsiyet ve kıdem değişkenlerine göre incelenmesi. *Türkiye Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 14(1), 237-250.
30. Özdemir, İ., 2003. Öğretmenlerin işbaşında yetiştirilmesinde okul yöneticisinin rolü. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*. 9 (35), 448-465.
31. Özden, Y., 1998. Eğitimde dönüşüm, eğitimde yeni değerler. Ankara: Pegem Yayıncılık.
32. Özgür, E.Ö., 2015. Algılanan örgütsel prestij, örgütsel özdeşleşme ve öğrenci başarısı arasındaki ilişkilerin incelenmesi. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Mevlana Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Konya.

33. Polat, M., 2009. Örgütsel özdeşleşmenin öncülleri ve ardılları üzerine bir saha çalışması. Yayınlanmamış Doktora tezi. Uludağ Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Bursa.
34. Pratt, M. G., 1998. To be or not to be? Central questions in organizational identification. Identity in organizations: Developing theory through conversations, ed. D. Whetten ve P. Godfrey, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 171-207.
35. Reade, C., 2001. Antecedents of organizational identification in multinational corporations: Fostering psychological attachment to the local subsidiary and the global organization. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 12 (8), 1269-1291.
36. Riketta, M., 2005. Organizational identification: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 66, 358-384.
37. Şirin, E., 2018. Örgütsel prestij algısı ile çalışanların örgüte bağlılıkları arasındaki ilişkide lider üye etkileşiminin rolü üzerine bir araştırma. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Marmara Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
38. Smidts, A., Pruyn, A. T. H., and Van Riel, C. B., 2001. The impact of employee communication and perceived external prestige on organizational identification. *Academy of Management Journal*, 44(5), 1051-1062.
39. Tajfel, H. (1972). La categorisation sociale (social categorization). Introduction à la Psychologie Sociale, ed. S. Moscovici, Paris, Larousse, 272-302.
40. Tajfel, H., and Turner, J. C. (1979). An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. *The Social Psychology Of Intergroup Relations*, 33(47), 74.
41. Tak, B., and Çiftçioğlu, A., 2009. Algılanan örgütsel prestij ile örgütsel bağlılık ve örgütsel özdeşleşme arasındaki ilişkilerin incelenmesine yönelik bir araştırma. *Akdeniz Üniversitesi İİBF Dergisi*, 18, 100-116.
42. Tak, B., and Aydemir, B. A., 2004. Örgütsel özdeşleşme üzerine iki görgül çalışma, 12. Ulusal Yönetim ve Organizasyon Kongresi Bildiri Kitabı, 27-29.
43. Taşkın, S., 2016. Öğretmenlerin örgütsel destek ve örgütsel özdeşleşme düzeyleri ile insiyatif iklimi arasındaki ilişki. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Bolu
44. Türk Dil Kurumu (TDK), Güncel Türkçe sözlük," İnternet Kaynağı; www.tdk.gov.tr. Erişim: 03.04.2018
45. Tutar, H., 2014. Örgütsel psikoloji. Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.
46. Tüzün, İ.K., 2006. Örgütsel güven, örgütsel kimlik ve örgütsel özdeşleşme ilişkisi: uygulamalı bir çalışma. Yayınlanmış Doktora Tezi. Gazi Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Ankara.
47. Tüzün, İ. K. and Çağlar, İ., 2008. Örgütsel özdeşleşme kavramı ve iletişim etkinliği ilişkisi. *Journal of Yaşar University*. 3(9). 1011-1027.
48. Tüzün, İ. K. and Çağlar, İ., 2009. Investigating the antecedents of organizational identification. *Doğuş Üniversitesi Dergisi*, 10 (2), 284-293.
49. Uğurlu, C. T. and Ceylan, N., 2013. Öğretmenlerin, okullarına ilişkin örgütsel imaj algılarının bazı değişkenler açısından incelenmesi. *Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 32(2). 301-322.

50. Yetim, A. E., 2010. Genel liselerde örgütsel iletişim ile öğretmenlerin örgütsel özdeşleşmeleri arasındaki ilişki. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Gazi Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
51. Yıldız, K., 2013. Öğretmenlerin örgütsel özdeşleşmeleri ile örgütsel iletişimleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Bilimleri, 13(1), 251-272.
52. Yörük, S. and Sağban, Ş., 2012. Okul müdürlerinin kültürel liderlik rollerinin öğretmenlerin örgütsel bağlılık düzeyine etkisi. Turkish Studies- International Periodical for the Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic, 7(3), 2795-2813.

Kaya Yıldız
THE EFFECTS OF ORGANIZATIONAL PRESTIGE ON ORGANIZATIONAL IDENTIFICATION:
A CASE STUDY IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).